

scale. Of 75 entries, 6 scored 1; 3, 3; 59, 5; and 7, 7 (see table). The six most resistant entries were from Sri Lanka. □

Thrips resistance rating of rice varieties, Jiangsu, China.

Reaction rating	Variety name ^a
1	Dahanala (15663), Dahanala 682 (50729), Kalubalawee (7717 & 15184), Kalu Heenati (15745 & 31431).
3	Kaluheenati (7750), Madael (15234), Wannu Dahanala (11726).
5	ADT22 (5901), ASD4 (5814), ASD7 (6303), Balamawe (15276), BJ1 (256, 3711, & 45195), BW78 (26915), Chandina (36420), CO 23 (6042), CO 27 (26843), Dahanala (15202 & 15650), Demala Kotan (40787), Gangala (7733, 15207, & 15259), Gona-baru (7809), H105 (158), Heenati (8964), Herath Banda (15304, 15362, 15378, 15632, 15748, 31412, & 31431), Jeeraga Samba (49732), Kalubalawee (7702), Kaluheenati (11996), Kalu Heenati (15568, 31432, 31433, 31434, 31435, 36267, & 36268), Kaohsiung Sen Yu 185 (38892), Madael (7722, 7727, 11701, & 15426), MRC 505 (39519), Perunel (15473), Ptb 33 (19325), Sinna Sivappu (15444), Sudu Hondarawala (15541), Suduru Samba (11671, 15237, 15272, & 36390), Sudurvi 305 (3475), Thunmar hamara (15226), TKM 2 (6034), TKM 6 (237, 6216, 35185), TNR 1 (9913), Utri Rajapan (16684).
7	Kuribit Puti (26882), Nira (1749, & 6309), Suduru Samba (14354), Sugadas (or Godavari Samba 50163), TKM6 (28571), Wulan Rua (19194).
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^aIRRI accession no. are in parentheses.

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization COLD TOLERANCE

VL Dhan 16: a medium-maturing, cold-tolerant rice for irrigated conditions

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We evaluated many advanced breeding lines to identify a suitable cold-tolerant variety for irrigated valleys at 900 m to 1,500 m altitudes. Some selections from IR1846 (J. P. 5/Y. R. L. I) were promising. One selection performed well in regional and national trials. It was released by the State Varietal Release Committee in 1984 as VL Dhan 16.

VL Dhan 16 is medium tall, compact, and stiff-strawed with medium tillering and light green leaves. Panicles are long and compact with good spikelet fertility and threshability. The husk and apiculus are straw-colored. Grains are medium-

Grain yield of VL Dhan 16 in multilocal trials, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	1980 (2)	1981 (4)	1982 (4)	1983 (4)	Mean
VL Dhan 16	4.3	5.4	4.5	4.2	4.6
VL 8	4.3	3.7	3.2	2.8	3.5
VLK 39	3.6	3.9	3.4	2.5	3.4
Thapachini	3.5	3.8	3.8	2.8	3.5

^aNumbers in parentheses indicate test locations.

sized with red kernels, nonglutinous endosperm, and good cooking quality. VL Dhan 16 has good blast and stem borer resistance and is cold tolerant.

In 14 multilocal yield trials during 4 yr, VL Dhan 16 was compared with VL-8 (improved medium-maturity check), VLK 39 (improved early check), and Thapachini (a local check) (see table). □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Salinity and sodicity tolerance in rice

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In a study of salinity and sodicity tolerance in rice, 40-d-old M1-48 seedlings were transplanted in pots in soils with EC 2.8, 7.0, 11.2, or 15.9 dS/m and pH 8.2, 9.5, 9.8, or 10.0. Exchangeable sodium

1. Effect of salinity (a) and sodicity (b) on percent reduction of grain yield and Na⁺ content of mature shoots of M1-48.